

Oxidation of liquid paraffins

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Abstract : Alkylhydroperoxides formed initially as the products of paraffin oxidation undergo decomposition to give alcohols, ketones etc. The further oxidation of these products yields carboxylic acids. The transition metal salts like stearates of Mn, Co and Cr and acetylacetonates of Mn, Co, Cr, Mo and complexes of metals like Ru, Pd, Ni etc. can accelerate the decomposition. Temperature directly influences the radical decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions. The rate of C-H bond activation depends not only upon the nature (primary, secondary and tertiary) but also their distance from the chain end. The oxidation of n-butane to maleic anhydride is the only commercialized process of paraffins. Higher rate of oxidation of the partial oxidation products than the starting paraffin and the irreversible deactivation of the catalysts have to be addressed. Selective photo-catalytic oxidation at ambient conditions may be the answer to use the readily available paraffin sources economically.

Keywords : Paraffin oxidation, C-H bond activities, hydroperoxides, decomposition products, catalysts, selective oxidation.

Introduction

Engler¹ showed the possibility of obtaining fatty acids from higher paraffins. The industrial application of paraffin oxidation^{2,3} was carried out by oxidizing paraffins with air at 130 to 135 °C to obtain fatty acids. Kelber mentioned the usage of manganese compounds as catalysts⁴ for paraffin oxidation. The technology and technical aspects^{5,6} of paraffin oxidation of particularly unbranched paraffins of C₂₀ to C₃₅ at 120 °C in the presence of manganese salts were described. Oxidation of medium chain paraffins of C₁₀ to C₁₈ lead to the production of the secondary alcohols^{7,8} with the corresponding chain lengths which can be subjected further to obtain different products.

Hydroperoxide formation and C-H bond reactivity

Rieche predicted the formation of alkylhydroperoxide⁹ as the primary product of the oxidation of paraffins. Ivanov isolated¹⁰ the corresponding hydroperoxide in the oxidation of n-heptane. As the kinetic chain length of paraffins by autoxidation is generally lower than 5, the yield of the hydroperoxide in the primary step of the oxidation is considerably lower. Besides the hydroperoxide, alcohols and ketones, corresponding to the chain termination between secondary peroxyradicals¹¹ are also expected. It

was concluded that by relatively lower temperatures of 100–120 °C, the oxidation of n-paraffin takes place preferably through hydroperoxide. The mode and the mechanism of oxidation of paraffin differ from olefin¹² and acetylene^{13–19} hydrocarbons to a greater extent. At higher reaction temperatures, the importance of hydroperoxide decreases due to increase in the rate of initiation and decrease of the kinetic chain length because the peroxyradicals under chain termination react to give alcohols and ketones. The same alcohols and ketones are formed generally as secondary products when the hydroperoxides undergo decomposition.

Autoxidation could be a good method for cetane number improvement²⁰ of diesel and kerosene due to the hydroperoxides produced. Alkanes having a lower carbon number produced more hydroperoxides because the hydroperoxide concentration of the alkane is dependent on both its hydroperoxide production ability and its molecular weight. The autoxidation mechanism is generated as Scheme 1.

Rate parameters for nine types of reactions, which are supposed to be important in the low temperature chemistry of alkane oxidation^{21–23} were reported. The conversion of alkanes to oxygen-containing compounds with

Initiation

Propagation

Termination

Scheme 1. Autoxidation mechanism of hydrocarbons.

molecular oxygen catalyzed by transition metal²⁴ is one of the most important and fundamental transformation in industrial chemistry^{25,26}.

If the oxidation is carried out in the presence of the typical oxidation catalysts e.g. Mn or Co salts, the peroxides formed can be iodometrically estimated as their isolation is not possible as decomposition of the hydroperoxide is favoured because of the presence of catalyst. By paraffin oxidation processes, in short reaction times and in lower turnovers, alcohols and ketones with unchanged carbon chain are preferably obtained.

Ivanov¹⁰ considered the isolated hydroperoxide from the heptane oxidation mixture as 2-hydroperoxyheptane. Pritzkow and co-workers²⁷ concluded that all secondary hydroperoxy heptanes were formed in relatively comparable amounts. It was also shown that all the secondary C-H bonds present in different positions were attacked

with almost the same reaction velocities. Similar results were also reported in the oxidation of n-nonane, n-decane, n-dodecane and n-octadecane²⁸. The exact data about the relative reaction rates of C-H bonds at different positions for the oxidation of n-decane was shown by Benton and Wirth²⁹. The results obtained by IR spectroscopy were confirmed in many cases by gas chromatographic methods³⁰⁻³².

A secondary C-H bond was 10 to 20 times easily attacked than a primary C-H bond. The reactivity of the secondary C-H bond at second position was slightly more than the one at third position. The reactivity of the secondary C-H bond decreases as its distance increases from the chain end of the paraffin. This follows in general the regularity shown in radical substitutions of n-paraffins³³.

Alkyl peroxy radical formed as intermediate by the primary attack on C-H bond of a paraffin can react pref-

erably with a C-H bond of another molecule of the paraffin intermolecularly and also intramolecularly.

Such intramolecular C-H bond cleavages through peroxy radicals appear in the case of autoxidation of di-tertiary paraffins when the tertiary C-H bonds are present in 1,3-position with respect to each other. Oxidation of alkanes catalyzed by Fe₂ (μ-carboxylato) complexes showed stereospecific transfer³⁴ of an oxygen atom from H₂O₂ to C-H bonds in alkanes. The C-H bond cleavage in the intermediate peroxyradicals is possible due to its rearrangement to a six member transition state³⁵. The intramolecular hydrogen atom abstraction in the intermediate peroxy radicals can take place to a less extent in the oxidation of n-paraffins. The reaction must also lead to the formation of bifunctional compounds like dihydroperoxide, hydroperoxy alcohols, hydroperoxy ketones, diketones etc. The composition of such bifunctional products with unchanged hydrocarbon rest is very low in the case of paraffins of C₅-C₁₆. The intramolecular hydrogen atom abstraction is shown possible in general in the case of the peroxy radicals formed in n-paraffin oxidation. The ratio of intramolecular hydrogen atom abstraction to intermolecular abstraction is shown to be between 0.1 to 0.2, although it is greater for n-hexadecane than n-pentane. The ratio increases with increase of temperature.

Rieche⁹ presumed that the hydroperoxides formed in the paraffin oxidation as primary products undergo decomposition through the cleavage of the carbon chain. But Langenbeck and Pritzkow³⁶⁻³⁹ on the basis of the examination of the oxidation of alcohols and Tetralin⁴⁰ came to a conclusion that the decomposition of secondary hydroperoxides preferably lead to the formation of the ketones and alcohols.

This conclusion is further established experimentally⁴¹ in the oxidation of n-pentane, n-hexane, n-heptane and n-decane. At high temperatures, during the decomposition of the secondary hydroperoxide, the fragmentation of the

alkoxy radical formed as intermediate also takes place⁴²

As a result of this, the corresponding hydrocarbon R'-H and R'-OH are formed. The degree of the ratio of fragmentation to total reaction is very low below the temperatures of 150 °C or under the normal conditions of the paraffin oxidation. By kinetic isotopic methods⁴³, decane hydroperoxide decomposition under the conditions of the oxidation at 150 °C lead to 55% of the hydroperoxide to ketones, 26 to 30% secondary alcohols and 11 to 18% lower alcohols and lower carboxylic acids. The presence of lower primary alcohols in the products of the oxidation of paraffins is doubtless due to the fragmentation of the secondary alkoxy radicals. The decomposition of the primarily formed hydroperoxide can be enhanced through transition metal salts and complexes. The order of activity² is generally Co > Mn > Cu > Ni > Fe ≥ Zn. In the absence of oxygen, more alcohols than ketones are formed although under normal conditions of paraffin oxidation, more ketones than the alcohols are formed as the alcohols formed are further oxidized to ketones. Therefore at 120 °C in the absence of catalysts and also with Mn or Co salts about 60% ketones and 40% alcohols were formed although slightly more ketones were formed with Cr salts. Pritzkow and co-workers⁴⁴ studied the decomposition of alkylhydroperoxides by different catalysts to find out the product selectivity.

Further oxidation of hydroperoxide-decomposition products

Alcohols and ketones formed primarily by the chain termination and by the decomposition of the hydroperoxides are oxidized further with higher rates. Their rate of oxidation is more than that of the starting paraffin. In the case of the oxidation of n-decane, n-decanol was attacked 6 times more than n-decane. In general, the rate of paraffin oxidation proceeds as starting paraffin < ketone < alcohols in the case of oxidation of cyclohexane⁴⁵.

The oxidation of secondary alcohols leads mainly to ketones⁴⁶. Alcohols formed by the fragmentation reactions are oxidized to carboxylic acids via aldehydes. It should be taken into consideration that if the attack takes

place at the non activated secondary C-H bonds of the alkyl rest with comparable rate like the attack to the -OH group attached to geminal C-H bonds, not only the carboxylic acids with the same number of carbon atoms but also hydroxy acids with shorter carbon chain length can form. The oxidation of alcohols to ketones studied on model substances like isopropanol⁴⁷ and cyclohexanal⁴⁸ was reported. In the absence of catalysts, one obtains the corresponding compounds and hydrogen peroxide most likely via the hydroperoxyalkylhydroperoxides.

The hydroxyalkylhydroperoxide can also undergo decomposition through cleavage of O-O peroxide bond to give the radical which can further undergo fragmentation easily.

This reaction shall take place much easily in the presence of catalysts. The significance of this fragmentation under the conditions of paraffin oxidation is not well known and indeed, it should be considered that this reaction is jointly responsible for the formation of lower alcohols in paraffin oxidation besides fragmentation by the decomposition of the secondary alkyl hydroperoxides. Further oxidation of the ketones takes place through α -hydroperoxy ketones⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ formed by radical chain reaction. The α -hydroperoxy ketones decompose to aldehydes and carboxylic acids under acid catalysis^{52,53}, thermal^{54,55} conditions or catalysis through transition metals⁵⁵.

Hock rearrangement is a special case of the acid catalyzed decomposition. Surprisingly, it takes place even in the presence of carboxylic acids^{52,53}. The probable mechanism of the decomposition should be through ionic fragmentation.

The decomposition of pure, crystalline β,β -diphenylpropiomesitylene hydroperoxide⁵⁶ in methanol under the influence of benzoic acid gave free mesitylene carboxylic acid but not mesitylene carboxylic methyl ester. By the ionic fragmentation as shown above, the acyl cation must give the corresponding methyl ester with the nucleophilic solvent, methanol.

The decomposition of α -hydroperoxy ketones in thermal and through the transition metal compounds proceeds via radical fragmentation.

This reaction is responsible for the formation of considerable amounts of carbon monoxide and the consecutive products of the alkyl radical R^{\cdot} i.e. R-H, R-OH in the decomposition of α -hydroperoxy ketones with Co or Mn-salts.

When the oxidative attack of the ketones takes place at α -position and not at other positions and also on not activated C-H bonds, the rate of oxidation of ketones is independent of the chain length. In reality, the $k_p/\sqrt{2k_t}$ oxidisabilities of a large number of C₅ to C₁₀ ketones are in accordance within the limits⁵⁷ of error. The findings correspond to the experimental results of the oxidation of C₉ to C₁₃ ketones which gave 70 to 90% carboxylic acids

as expected due to selective attack at α -position and 10 to 30% carboxylic acids with lower carbon chain length. It is known that the carboxylic acids with lower carbon chain length are obtained to an extent of 10 to 30% due to oxidation of non activated (non α -position) C-H bonds.

It is established⁵⁸ that the products of the oxidation of higher ketones contain not only aldehydes and monocarboxylic acids, the bifunctional compounds with unchanged carbon framework but also γ -lactones, lactides etc. These findings were confirmed by Rif *et al.*⁵⁹. The presence of γ -lactones was identified by IR and gas chromatographic methods. The formation of hydroxy acids can be explained via the trifunctional oxidation products with unchanged carbon atom framework which form from peroxyradicals through intramolecular radical C-H bond cleavage.

This is of course can not be a general mechanism because through these routes, only β -hydroxy carboxylic acids can form. It must be established that the esters are formed by the oxidation of ketones. Methyl ethyl ketone yielded at 100 °C besides acetic acid mainly ethyl methanoate⁶⁰. This is the likely pathway of the formation of ethyl methanoate in the oxidation of n-butane^{61,62}.

Ethyl methanoate could be formed from methyl ethyl ketone through Baeyer-Villiger oxidation^{63,64} with peracetic acid.

Baeyer-Villiger reaction was shown responsible for the formation of ϵ -caprolactam in the oxidation of cyclohexane.

The reaction takes place very slowly with higher aliphatic ketones than cyclohexanone and therefore the importance of this reaction in the oxidation of paraffins is disputed. Another radical reaction mechanism through which an ester formation by the oxidation of ketones could not be considered as an evidence.

Further, oxidation of aldehydes formed by the decomposition of α -hydroperoxy ketones and also by the radical fragmentation of alkylhydroperoxides lead to the

formation of the corresponding carboxylic acids⁶⁵ via peracids.

The first step of this reaction takes place by radical mechanism with large kinetic lengths ($\gamma = 100$ to 1000)⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸ while the second step is an ionic one taking place through an adduct from peracid and aldehyde⁶⁹.

The intermediate acyl radical which forms by the radical oxidation of aldehydes can react not only with oxygen but also can undergo decarbonylation⁷⁰.

The decarbonylation and also the radical decarboxylation of peracids⁷¹⁻⁷³ and the attack at the activated -CH₂ group at α-position is responsible in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes not only for the formation of the corresponding carboxylic acids but also the compounds (e.g. hydrocarbons, alcohols, aldehydes, carboxylic acids) with one carbon atom less in the carbon chain. The extent of the radical decarbonylation as well as the radical decarboxylation increases with the increase in the temperature.

It is known that acid anhydrides⁷⁴ can be formed by the oxidation of aldehydes. The deciding reaction step here is the oxidation of the intermediate acyl radical which takes place through the transition metal ions especially through Cu-ions. Whether this reaction is possible under the conditions of the oxidation of paraffins is not surely evident.

The reaction could explain the formation of esters but it should be taken into consideration that for the formation of acid anhydride, the especially effective Cu-catalysts are not generally employed in the oxidation of paraffins. Carboxylic acids are mostly the end products of the paraffin oxidation. But they can undergo further oxidation. It is understandable that the C-H bonds at least

which are nearer the carboxylic group should possess the reactivity comparable with the oxidation of C-H bonds in n-paraffins. The authors initially engaged with the oxidation of carboxylic acids considered a preferential oxidation on C-H bonds at β-position⁷⁴. Berezin supported the β-oxidation observations by taking the ¹⁴C-labelled carboxylic acids where ¹⁴CO₂ is cleaved off. But later it was established that carboxylic acids under the conditions of

autoxidation according to the equations,

decarboxylate and therefore one can't conclude that the formation of ¹⁴CO₂ in the autoxidation of ¹⁴C-labelled carboxylic acid is due to β-oxidation only. Pritzko⁷⁵ showed that caporic acid methylester was attacked at all secondary C-H bonds by molecular oxygen and there was no preference for β-C-H bond attack. From the statistics of the attack at C-H bonds, it was shown that the velocity of oxidation decreases with increase in the chain length of the carboxylic acids. The reactivity differs in the same way as in the case of primary, secondary C-H bonds in n-paraffins or in ketones.

Formation of esters in the oxidation of n-paraffins

In the oxidation of n-paraffins, besides free carboxylic acids, esters were also reported in the oxidation mixtures to the extent of 50 to 70% of the total free acids⁷⁶. A part of the esters like lactones and lactides could be

removed by saponification of the paraffin oxidation mixture with NaOH. Lactones and respectively the hydroxyacids responsible would form through the oxidation of ketones. They should also be expected as products of oxidation of secondary alcohols when the attack doesn't take place at the C-H bond to which the -OH group is attached as well as products of further oxidation of carboxylic acids.

The follow up of the ester and acid content during the oxidation of n-paraffins show that esters and acids form side by side from the beginning. Consequently esters are not the consecutive products of the conversion of the carboxylic acids formed in the paraffin oxidation with the secondary alcohols formed at the same time. Indeed the reaction rate of carboxylic acids with secondary alcohols under the conditions of paraffin oxidation is so low that this reaction doesn't have a considerable part in the formation of esters⁷⁷.

Langenbeck and Pritzkow³⁹ considered that the ester formed in the paraffin oxidation could be due to Baeyer-Villiger reaction of the ketones with peracids, both formed as intermediates. This reaction is indeed relatively slower in the case of high molecular weight open chain ketones and therefore, it is questionable whether this reaction has considerable part for the formation of esters in the oxidation of n-paraffins. There is no proof for Berezin formulated radical oxidation of ketones to esters and also the formation of intermediate acid anhydride is not established and therefore it should be seen that the formation of a true ester in the paraffin oxidation is not clear. But it is true that esters are formed besides lactones and lactides.

Composition of carboxylic acids from the paraffin oxidation

Normally the mono carboxylic acids are the aspired products of paraffin oxidation. By statistical attack at secondary C-H bonds of the paraffin employed and in the case of selective further oxidation of reaction's intermediate products (e.g. alcohols at geminal, ketones at the α -positioned C-H bonds), one expects that the carboxylic acids with medium chain length form around 50% of the starting hydrocarbon. By the oxidation of C_n paraffins, the carboxylic acids C_3 to C_{n-2} should form in comparable amounts and the carboxylic acids C_{n-1} to C_n should

form in lower amounts (as it is formed only by the oxidation of a methyl group). Formic acid is expected to form in considerable amounts when the aldehyde formed as intermediate undergoes oxidation of the C-H bonds at α -position.

Grüns³ conclusions that although all carboxylic acids from C_1 to C_n are formed, the ones with lower carbon chain lengths predominate were further established^{78,79}. The complete analysis of the carboxylic acids formed in the paraffin oxidation is highly difficult as the acids with less than C_4 are water soluble liquids. It is sure that the molar quantities of formic acid and acetic acids are more than the other acids. The effect of the catalysts employed is not perceptible. This points to the fact that by lower turnovers, the further oxidation of the carboxylic acids formed has no remarkable significance. The yield of higher acids from C_{n-4} against the lower acids decreases considerably. It is not because that these acids are oxidized further at higher velocities but because that those intermediate products responsible for the formation of higher acids are relatively easily converted to higher functional oxidation products. A further oxidation of mono carboxylic acids is naturally possible and by high turnovers, it commands significantly on the distribution of the mono carboxylic acids. One finds the corresponding di-carboxylic acids further in the products of the technical paraffin oxidation⁸⁰ and they can be obtained as main products by increasing the turnovers. The processing of the reaction mixtures becomes very difficult as the paraffin oxidation is not employed to synthesize di-carboxylic acids. Besides the homologue fatty acids and di-carboxylic acids formed from the former, hydroxy acids (partly converted to lactones or lactides) and keto acids are also present in the reaction mixtures of paraffin oxidation. The complete analysis of these compounds is extraordinarily difficult and needs high precision of analysis. The Varrentrapp reaction⁸¹ is responsible for the formation of mono carboxylic acids in the case of hydroxy acids.

Selective oxidation

A considerable urgency to replace the technologies with more efficient alternatives using dioxygen, hydrogen peroxide or other easily accessible and environmentally friendly oxidants for the conversion of petroleum

products to valuable commodity chemicals is in the offing. An integrated multi step process for selective partial oxidation of alkanes to alcohols, ethers or alkenes that provides unprecedented product control using dioxygen as the ultimate oxidant in a sequential zone flow reactor⁸², unique approaches^{83,84} with strong economic rationales⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷ has come into focus with. The overall transformation was represented as Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Selective oxidation of alkanes to alcohols.

There is the possibility of using paraffins directly by the petrochemical industries as they are more economical and less toxic as compared to aromatics. The oxidation of n-butane to maleic anhydride has been commercialized⁸⁸. Selective oxidation and oxidehydrogenation of paraffins⁸⁹⁻⁹² have been far from industrial interest as low yields of the final products are frequently observed due to

- (i) The reactivity of the product of partial oxidation is more than the starting hydrocarbon.
- (ii) Irreversible deactivation of the catalyst. In addition to the problems associated with the presence

of consecutive reactions of oxidative degradation upon desired product and the undesired contribution.

Acetic acid, propanoic acid and solvents such as esters and lower ketones were industrially produced from butane⁹³ and light gasoline⁹⁴. The mechanism using metalloprophyrins⁹⁵ involves the hydrogen atom abstraction from the substrate, R-H by a reactive iron-oxo intermediate followed by rapid transfer of the metal-bound oxygen atom to an intermediate caged alkyl radical.

Selective oxidation and functionalization of alkanes under mild conditions is an exciting scientific and economic goal⁹⁶. Selective formation of cyclohexyl hydroperoxide from cyclohexane was achieved in the presence of hydrogen peroxide and dinuclear iron(III) complex^{97, 98} with μ -alkoxo bridges. Hydroperoxide formation⁹⁹ based on MOPAC (AM1) calculations¹⁰⁰ are available.

HOMO and LUMO of n-octane

The catalytic activity of the polymer-bound Mn^{IV} -triazacyclononane derivative system containing H_2O_2 and CH_3COOH was proved to be efficient in the oxidation of alkanes^{101,102} leading to the formation of corresponding alkyl hydroperoxides.

Phthalimide N-oxyl (PINO) radical, generated from N-hydroxy phthalimide (NHPI-carbon radical producing catalyst) abstracts a hydrogen atom from the carbon-hydro-

gen bond of various hydrocarbons including alkanes, alcohols, ethers, acetals and aldehydes under mild conditions, and forms the corresponding carbon radical with high selectivity and high catalytic efficiency^{103,104}. Cyclohexane was oxidized to adipic acid in one step with dioxygen (1 atm) by using NHPI compound with a small amount of Mn complex¹⁰⁵.

A novel O₂ insertion into a Pt^{IV}-hydride bond to form a stable Pt^{IV} hydroperoxide compound is significant as the reactant is a Pt^{IV} alkyl hydroperoxide complex¹⁰⁶ analogous to those produced via oxidative addition of alkane C-H bonds, thus promising for the development of commercially viable homogenous catalytic alkane oxidation. A dual mechanistic pathways involving

Scheme 3. Mechanism for the oxidation of cyclohexane.

predominantly a metal based oxidant proceeding in a heterolytic manner was proposed (Scheme 3) by Tembe *et al.*^{107,108} in the oxidation of cyclohexane by *tert*-butylhydroperoxide using polynuclear manganese(III) Schiff base complexes. Oxidation of cyclohexane to

cyclohexanol and cyclohexanone in the presence of salen complexes¹⁰⁹ of iron(III) and manganese(III) as catalyst, using hydrogen peroxide and *tert*-butylhydroperoxide was reported.

Highly effective oxidation of alkanes by *tert*-butylhydroperoxide¹¹⁰ or peracetic acid¹¹¹ in the presence of lower-valent rhenium catalysts and the aerobic oxidation¹¹² in the presence of Ru, Fe and Cu catalysts are known. Intermediacy of oxo-ruthenium^{113,114} rather than alkoxy radical was proposed.

A large number of reactions catalysed by transition metal containing catalysts involving co-reductants and without them, couldn't add till date anymore successful commercial process²⁴ to the existing one i.e. the conversion of n-butane to maleic anhydride.

Oxidation under irradiation

Saturated hydrocarbons such as cyclohexane, n-hexane, propane, adamantane, cumene etc. were oxidized in the presence of dioxygen by a neutral luminescent *trans*-dioxoosmium(VI) complex under UV-Vis irradiation (Scheme 4) to either alcohols, ketones or aldehydes^{115,116}.

Scheme 4. Aerobic oxidation of saturated alkanes with metal-oxo complexes through irradiation.

Selective photo-catalytic conversion of cyclohexane into cyclohexanol with higher selectivity with molecular oxygen over quantum confined iron doped TiO₂ (Q-TiO₂/Fe³⁺) nanoparticles¹¹⁷ under visible irradiation and mild conditions^{118,119} with the following mechanism (Scheme 5) is to be considered as a mile stone.

Charge pair generation

Charge trapping

Charge release and migration

Interfacial charge transfer

Scheme 5. Selective photo-catalytic conversion of cyclohexane into cyclohexanol.

The reactions of coupling between the alkane oxidation and the nitrous compounds and a detailed chemical kinetic modelling¹²⁰ investigations reproduce the temperature dependence of the conversion of the reactants and the species concentration profiles versus the residence time in the reactor.

Oxidation of branched paraffins

In general the free radical substitution is the expected reaction of saturated hydrocarbons. The reactivity of different C-H bonds vis-a-vis peroxy radicals is in the increas-

ing order of primary C-H < secondary C-H < tertiary C-H bond. In the case of gas phase oxidation at 350 °C, the relative reaction rates are in the ratio of 1 : 4 : 11. Even in liquid phase oxidation of the branched paraffins, the tertiary C-H bonds react preferably. Also in the case of isobutane^{121,122} and isopentane¹²³ (2-methylbutane) in liquid phase oxidation at 100–150 °C, the corresponding tertiary hydroperoxides were the first reaction products. Sutton and co-workers showed the relative velocity of a tertiary C-H bond to a primary C-H bond in the oxidation of 5-methyl nonane in the ratio of 50 : 01. Rust examined the liquid phase oxidation of a doubly branched alkane and concluded the formation of a bis-hydroperoxide³⁵ even at lower turnovers. The intramolecular C-H cleavage should be responsible for it. Such hydrogen transfers take place in considerable proportions only when the six membered transition states are possible and when the C-H bond undergoing the cleavage is a tertiary one. Rusts findings in the oxidation of 2,3-dimethylpentane and 2,6-dimethylheptane that no noticeable bis-hydroperoxide was formed by lower turnovers were confirmed by other authors¹²⁴⁻¹²⁶. Higher simple branched paraffins gave higher yields of bifunctional oxidation products^{127,128} compared to the unbranched paraffins. It obviously points to the claim that those peroxy radicals whose peroxy groups are attached to the third or fourth carbon atom to the tertiary C-H bond react through intramolecular H-transfer. The decomposition of the tertiary hydroperoxide under the conditions of hydrocarbon oxidation was studied in the case of tertiary-amyl hydroperoxide. The main reactions of the decompositions in the presence of isopentane as solvent are the fragmentation of tertiary alkoxy radicals and H-atom abstraction from the solvent.

Ethanol and acetic acid which are the consecutive products of the ethyl radicals formed due to fragmentation are

obtained as reaction products besides acetone and tertiary-amyl alcohol. The decomposition of *tert*-butylhydroperoxide in isobutene as solvent takes place in analogous. It is considered that the oxidation of branched paraffins takes place in analogue to the oxidation of normal branched paraffins. The oxidizabilities and reaction velocities of the elementary reactions of the oxidation of n-paraffins like 2,3-dimethylbutane¹²⁹, 2,4-dimethylpentane, 2,4,6-trimethylheptane and isobutane¹³⁰⁻¹³² were reported. The oxidizability of n-paraffins increases as expected with increase in chain length. The chain termination velocities do not differ substantially. The chain propagation velocities¹³³ increase with the increase in the chain length. It is nearly the same trend in isoparaffins. It is dependent upon together with that in the isoparaffins compared to the n-paraffins not only especially the active tertiary C-H bond but also three extra primary C-H bonds present. By the transition of n-paraffin to isomeric isoparaffin four secondary C-H bonds disappear while a tertiary and three C-H bonds newly form.

Conclusions

The direct use of paraffins which are readily available raw materials, economical and low in toxicity should be considered as alternative for conversion to oxidized products to fulfill the growing industrial needs. To achieve the goals, two vistas that require further investigations are :

- (i) To obtain a suitable catalyst with activity over a long period and selectivity to the required product through oxifunctionalisation and
- (ii) Selective photo-catalytic oxidation of alkanes with suitable photo-catalysts that can activate the relatively non reactive C-H bonds with molecular oxygen as oxidant under mild conditions.

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